

A Multi-Purpose Sensor for Composite Structures Based on a Piezo-Electric Film

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Abstract

In this study, a multi-purpose sensor for composite laminates is developed. The sensor is based on a piezo-electric film. A specialty charge amplifier was developed for signal conditioning for long time duration measurements. Experiments were conducted to show the utility of the sensor for static and dynamic strain measurement. By effectively isolating the piezo film for unidirectional strain, a method was developed to utilize the piezo sensor for general, in-plane strain sensing, regardless of the constitutive properties of the laminate. The results indicate that temperature compensation is necessary for applications over a wide range of temperatures. Non-destructive evaluation in through-transmission and pulse-echo modes were shown to be effective for measuring and quantifying damage in laminated structures. Using the piezo film as a sensor to detect impact, it was shown that an "event" as well as the onset of damage can be accurately measured. With standard acoustic emission equipment, the piezo film proved to be an effective direct substitution for typical piezo-crystals at a fraction of the cost and weight for acoustic emission monitoring in advanced composite laminates. The onset of damage, as well as damage location were accurately measured. The preliminary results indicate that the sensor is quite versatile, inexpensive and sensitive for a variety of sensing applications in advanced composite laminates. In particular, the electronics needed for signal conditioning are much less elaborate than typical sensors such as strain gages, piezoceramic sensors, thermocouples, etc.

1. Introduction

Advanced composite laminates are being utilized in primary aerospace structures. These materials can offer much to designers/analysts for tailoring properties for specific applications. However, the longevity of these materials can be more explicitly determined if the history and in-situ properties can be monitored throughout the lifetime of the structure. This has particular advantages since some of the statistical aspects which are assumed for longevity calculations can be quantified. In addition, if the complete history of a structure is known, the mission of the structure can be determined on a component basis. Consequently, a multi-purpose sensor which can accomplish the above would provide a means of monitoring the spectral loading and longevity of a structure.

In this study, a multi-purpose sensor for composite structures is explored. It is based on Kynar[™] piezo-electric film [1,2]. Little is documented on the use of these films for structural monitoring, but Reference 1 includes a good review and list of references of the theory and exploratory applications of piezo-electric films. These piezo films are manufactured from a polymeric polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF). A thin film is first stretched to obtain the polymeric structure as shown in Figure 1. The material is then heated to the Curie point (just below the melting point) and then poled. Poling is accomplished by subjecting the material to a strong electric field while the material is subjected to this temperature. The poled structure of the material is shown in Figure 2. When cooled below the Curie temperature, the material has a natural tendency to go to this orientation when subjected to strain. The piezo film thus develops an excess or deficiency in charge which makes them useful as sensors. The upper use temperature for the PVDF films is approximately 120 °C. When a conductive layer is applied to both sides of the film, it provides capacitance storing of the charge. However, this capacitance is small (on the order of 1 nf) and any measurement device can cause a drift. This is why piezo films typically perform better in dynamic situations than static situations (> 1 Hz).

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The advantage of piezo films over piezo crystals and ceramics are many. Piezo films are flexible and can be cut to any size. This makes them especially applicable for complicated geometries. Also, since these films possess a low sharpness of resonance (Q), they have a wide bandwidth (approximately 1 GHz) where as most piezo crystals are applicable over a narrow bandwidth. Since the piezo films are relatively compliant and can absorb more energy, they act as good receivers. However, as a result of this compliance, they do not possess the authority of a piezo crystal. Consequently, these films do not perform as well as piezo crystals for emitters or actuators.

2. Experimental Setup

Due to a charge leakage of the film, a charge amplifier was constructed to minimize leakage for static tests (< 1Hz). The test setup for data acquisition for charge produced by the piezo film is shown in Figure 3. In this figure, a capacitor is implemented to maintain the charge produced by the piezo film and is cascaded with another amplifier. This is necessary to compensate for the loss of charge versus time under constant displacement. For this setup the value of resistance for feedback in the inverting amplifier was chosen to be 3kΩ to provide an overall gain of approximately 0.3. As stated above, a displacement of dipoles produces a charge. As a result, these piezo films tend to produce charge under transient temperature fluctuations and may require more temperature compensation than was conducted here depending on the application. However, this simple circuit is much less complicated than that required for resistive strain gage amplification and has much better transient response than a typical strain gage amplifier.

3. Experimental Results - Strain Sensing

For preliminary assessment of the piezo film as a general transducer, an LDT1-028 film (30.2mm long by 12.7mm wide) manufactured by Pennwalt was chosen [1]. As indicated above, the piezo film exhibits orthotropic sensing properties. Data are available from the manufacturer for unidirectional stress states to determine the voltage in the three orthogonal directions (longitudinal, transverse and through-the thickness) of the film. However, based on the theory of operation presented in the introduction, the charge produced is dependent on displacements. Hence, the charge is not independent of constitutive properties. Consequently, prior to using the film for strain measurement, the voltage produced for unidirectional strain must be isolated and determined.

To isolate the in-plane components of strain (1,2 axes), a 90 degree specimen manufactured from Hercules AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy system was used. The in-plane constitutive properties of this material are shown in TABLE 1.

TABLE 1 Constitutive Properties of AS4/3501-6

Property	Value
E_{11} (GPa)	140.7
E_{22} (GPa)	9.0
G_{12} (GPa)	5.6
ν_{21}	0.019

Note that the Poisson's Ratio in the 2-1 direction is quite small which nearly decouples the film under unidirectional loading conditions. Hence, films can be mounted on this specimen and the sensitivities for unidirectional strain can be isolated. To determine this relationship, strain gages were mounted on a thick, 90 degree laminate perpendicular to and parallel to the fiber axis as shown in Figure 4. This coupon has a gage of 190.5 mm long by 63.5 mm wide. In addition, the piezo films were placed on the specimen with the 1 direction perpendicular to and parallel to the fiber axis. Typical stress-strain measurements as measured for this laminate are shown in Figure 5. Notice the extremely small transverse strain in the transverse direction as governed by the small ν_{21} in TABLE 1. The longitudinal and transverse film voltage outputs are shown in Figure 6. Hence, the unidirectional, in-plane voltage response of the film was calculated according to:

$$V_{11}e_1 + V_{22}e_1 = V1 \quad a)$$

$$V_{22}e_1 + V_{11}e_1 = V2 \quad b)$$

1)

where V_{11} is the response of the film for unidirectional strain along the longitudinal direction of the film (volts/percent strain), V_{22} is the response of the film in the transverse direction, e_1 is the measured strain in the longitudinal direction of the coupon, e_2 is the measured strain in the transverse direction of the coupon, V1 is the voltage output of the film oriented along the specimen axis and V2 is the voltage of the film oriented transverse to the axis of the laminate.

For unidirectional loading in the transverse direction, the e_t is quite small compared to e_l based on n_{21} in TABLE 1. Hence, inversion of Equation 1, represents a minor correction. Based on these tests, the value of V_{11} is 42.3 volts/% extensional strain and the value of V_{22} is 11.0 volts/% extensional strain for uniaxial strain loading.

If this sensor is to be useful for a wide variety of laminates, it is necessary for Equation 1 to hold for a wide variety of in-plane constitutive properties. Consequently, an aluminum sample was prepared and the voltage output was predicted using Equation 1. These results are shown in Figure 7. Good agreement is found between the predicted and measured values.

As a final test of the usefulness of the piezo film for strain measurement, a $[\pm 45]_k$ laminate was made. The in-plane constitutive properties are shown in TABLE 2. Note the high n_{xy} of the laminate, indicating significant contributions from transverse strains on V_1 and V_2 in Equation 1.

TABLE 2 Constitutive Properties of $[\pm 45]_k$ AS4/3501-6

<u>Property</u>	<u>Value</u>
E_x (GPa)	19.5
E_y (GPa)	19.5
G_{xy} (GPa)	33.9
ν_{xy}	0.750

Measured versus predicted results for the $[\pm 45]_k$ laminate in the elastic region are shown in Figure 8. Again, the predicted results compare favorably with measured results.

As stated above the mechanical strain produces a charge as a result of relative displacement of dipoles in the film. Hence, if the film also experiences shear, a net charge may be produced. To determine this effect, a film was mounted at 45 degrees with respect to the longitudinal loading axis. By rotating the longitudinal and transverse strains into the film axis, the total output of the film may be simply calculated as:

$$V_{tot} = \frac{(e_l + e_t)}{2} (V_{11} + V_{22}) + (e_l - e_t)V_{12} \quad 2)$$

where V_{tot} is the total output of the piezo film and V_{12} is the response of the film to shearing strain. Using the $[\pm 45]_k$ laminate for this response is especially applicable since the high Poisson's ratio reported in TABLE 2 minimizes the influence of the in-plane terms V_{11} and V_{22} . Using this specimen provides a value for V_{12} of -0.3 volts/% shear strain. This is two orders of magnitude lower than the V_{11} and V_{22} values. The sensitivity for in-plane strain of the film is summarized in TABLE 3.

TABLE 3 In-Plane Piezo Film Strain Sensitivity Constants

<u>Piezo-Strain Constant</u>	<u>Value (volts/% strain)</u>
V_{11}	42.3
V_{22}	11.0
V_{12}	-0.3

Consequently, using these data, the piezo film appears to be a good sensor for general in-plane strain measurements. By effectively isolating the in-plane response for unidirectional strain of the piezo film, a piezo rosette may be used for measuring general in-plane strain.

Since the displacement of dipoles produces a charge, these sensors are expected to be temperature sensitive. The films were mounted on an AS4/3401-6 $[+45/0/-45/90]_k$ quasi-isotropic laminate. The laminate was heated and cooled and the voltage output was monitored via the charge amplifier. These results are shown in Figure 9. The voltage output in Figure 9 is a result of the thermomechanical strains and the thermoelectric properties of the piezo film. The effects have not been isolated here. These results indicate that, while the piezo film may be an effective temperature sensor, compensation will be necessary for accurate strain measurements.

4. Experimental Results - Dynamic Response

Cyclic or Spectrum Loading Conditions

Under cyclic or transient loading greater than 1 Hz, the charge amplifier is not necessary. The losses are negligible and the capacitive effect of the metalized coating is sufficient for direct measurement. An example of this is shown in Figure 10. Here, the AS4/3401-6 [+45/0/-45/90]_{2s} quasi-isotropic laminate was cycled in tension and compression at from 50.0 MPa to -50.0 MPa ($\pm 918 \mu\text{-strain}$) which produced a maximum of 0.08 V output, sufficient for monitoring with conventional equipment. Consequently, for cyclic history monitoring of composite structures where the cyclic loading is greater than 1 Hz, the piezo film should serve as an adequate transducer with no charge amplification.

Transient or Impact Response

The Kynar film also proved to be adequate to monitor impact loading on a composite plate. A 101.6 mm wide by 152.4 mm long AS4/3501-6 [+45/0/-45/90]_{6s} laminate was simply supported and impacted with a 4.1 kg instrumented mass with a 12.7 mm diameter tup from a height of 0.18 m. A piezo film was placed on the laminate near, but not directly on the point of impact. The results of the load versus time and piezo film versus time is shown in Figure 11. Again, no charge amplifier was implemented. Damage formation in the specimen is typically seen as a significant load drop in the impact force versus time history. This response was also detected in the response of the piezo film. Consequently, with the entire history of a piezo sensor known, it may be possible to determine if any significant "event" has occurred in the structure.

5. Experimental Results - Non-Destructive Evaluation

Another useful application of the piezo film is with respect to Non Destructive Evaluation (NDE). This was studied in both a through-transmission and pulse echo mode. The through transmission mode is illustrated in Figure 12. In this figure, an AS4/3501-6 [+45/0/-45/90]_{6s}, 5.08 mm thick laminate with an implanted delamination was instrumented with films on and outside of the delaminated region. Typical through-transmission results for the receiver film are shown in Figure 13. Here a 240V, 230ns pulse was input to the sending film and sensed on the back side of the laminate as shown in Figure 12. The received signal, as well as a second reflection is shown in Figure 13. The voltage output of approximately 3.0 V is adequate for sensing. When the emitter and sensor films were laminated over the delaminations, virtually no pulse was received. Consequently, with a dense grid of emitters and receivers, a map of delaminations could be constructed, providing in-situ NDE monitoring.

As further demonstration of the utility of the piezo films for NDE applications, a UDT-01 film was used in a pulse-echo C-scan mode [1]. In the pulse-echo mode, a piezo film is used as both the emitter and receiver. The UDT-01 film is especially appropriate for this application since it has better through-the-thickness authority and sensitivity. A laminate was prepared with implanted, 25.4 mm diameter delaminations using teflon film inserts. Typical results for using the piezo film as a pulse-echo NDE transducer are shown in Figure 14 for the same input pulse of 240V. In this figure is shown the first and second reflections. Using time-of-flight measurements the delamination was found at a depth of approximately 1.17 mm compared to the actual, implanted depth of between 1.13 mm (front side) and 1.18 (back side) mm. Thus, not only can the delamination be located in-plane using the piezo film in a pulse-echo mode; the depth can be located as well. The UDT-01 piezo film was used for pulse-echo imaging as well. In Figure 15a is shown a two dimensional raster C-Scan image of an impact-damaged laminate using a 2 MHz piezo crystal transducer. Damage appears as the dark region based on peak amplitude of the reflected backwall signal. The same image was constructed with the UDT-01 film as shown in Figure 15b. The image in 15b is less sharp than the one shown in Figure 15a. The film was cantilevered with one end unconstrained in the imaging tank, and no attempt was made to constrain or focus the piezo film. In light of this the results are encouraging, and some additional development should preclude the slightly blurred image.

6. Experimental Results - Acoustic Emission

Since the piezo films have such a wide bandwidth and are quite sensitive, the possibility of employing them as Acoustic Emission (AE) transducers was explored. To demonstrate feasibility, two experiments were conducted to evaluate the response of the PVDF films to acoustic emission events and locations.

In the first experiment, two PVDF film sensors were located adjacent to piezo crystal Physical Acoustics Corporation (PAC) PICO 500 kHz sensors and monitored using a PAC 3400 data acquisition system. The test specimen was a thick, composite ring loaded in hydrostatic external compression as shown in Figure 16. These rings are manufactured from AS4/3501-6 and are approximately 203 mm in diameter with a 15.7 mm wall thickness. Sensors and films were placed at 0 degree and 180 degree locations and monitored during the test. The objective of this test was to determine if the PVDF sensor follows the same general trend as the PAC sensors. In the second experiment, three PVDF sensors were mounted on the inner radius at 0, 120 and 240 degree locations. This second test was conducted to determine if the failure site could be located using the piezo films.

The PVDF sensors developed for these experiments were constructed from two Pennwalt LDT1-028 films which were adhered together to shield the transducer from background noise during the experiments. In this manner, AE events which occur within the laminate can be more properly isolated.

The amplitude of event versus frequency results of the first experiment shows that the piezo films are comparable to the PAC sensors as shown in Figure 17. In this test, the threshold for the PAC transducer was set at 59 db gain, while the piezo film threshold was set at 60 db. In Figure 17, the cumulative event versus event duration is an indication of the severity of damage [3]. Although the response of the two sensors do not match on a point-by-point basis, the trends are similar. The measured response between piezo sensors is also scattered and these data are acceptable [3,4]. Thus, these piezo films may be used in place of piezo crystals without modification of existing AE hardware. This is especially advantageous since the piezo films cost approximately two orders of magnitude less than a typical piezo crystal.

Qualitative results from the second test are shown in Figure 18. Figure 18 is a plot of AE events received in the piezo film versus angle for the ring. These data show that the location of most significant AE activity corresponds to the site of fracture in the composite ring. Thus, using the piezo film as an AE sensor may provide a practical method for monitoring damage initiation and growth in composite structures.

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

A preliminary feasibility study for using piezo films for general-purpose sensing applications has been conducted. In this study, the piezo film has shown utility for strain measurement, transient response monitoring, Non-Destructive Evaluation (NDE) and Acoustic Emission (AE) monitoring (with event location identified) for advanced composite laminates. These preliminary results are quite encouraging and show much potential. Specific conclusions and recommendations are outlined below.

Strain Monitoring

By isolating the in-plane piezo strain response characteristics, the piezo film shows much potential for in-service monitoring of composite structures for general in-plane strains. The equations and data developed herein effectively isolate the performance of the film from the constitutive properties (including biaxiality or poisson coupling effects) of the structure to which it is adhered. In this manner, with the piezo strain coefficients known, a rosette may be applied to determine general, in-plane strains. Temperature compensation will be necessary if the film is used over a wide temperature range. It was found that a charge amplifier may be necessary to mitigate leakage of the film if the strain measurement needs to be conducted over a long period of time (> 1 sec).

Transient Response

If the loading is transient in nature (> 1Hz), a charge amplifier is not necessary and the output of the piezo film may be monitored directly using standard laboratory equipment. This has particular applications for monitoring spectrum loading in aerospace structures or to monitor significant "events" such as spike loading or impact for assessing the longevity of a structure.

Non Destructive Evaluation (NDE)

Using the piezo film in both a through-transmission or pulse-mode for ultrasonic inspection of composite laminates showed excellent potential both as an emitter and as a receiver. Consequently, a single film may be used in a passive mode for the above applications and in an active mode for NDE of a structure. Damage was easily located using the piezo films. Imaging was adequate, and with minor development, should be as good as current piezo crystal, pulse-echo transducers. While not explored in this study, a single sensor may be employed for impact detection and NDE. These results warrant further studies.

Acoustic Emission (AE) Monitoring

As a result of their sensitivity, the piezo films performed well as an AE transducer. Events were counted and located. These films performed as well as AE transducers costing as much as two orders of magnitude more. Thus, these films have applications for obtaining much more information during destructive testing of composite structures where the sensor may be sacrificed during the test.

Since these films perform so well over a wide variety of applications, they appear to offer much for use as general purpose sensors. Major limitations of PVDF films seem to be only the temperature sensitivity (requiring compensation) and upper limit temperature of 120 °C. However, using a single sensor is especially attractive since it precludes the application of expensive, redundant sensing systems. One sensor can be used in passive monitoring (i.e., strain, spectrum loading, impact, AE) to determine the longevity of a structure and can also

be used in an active mode (NDE) for quantifying damage. Ease of manufacturing, with direct interface to existing equipment, make piezo films an excellent candidate for such applications.

8. References

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9. Biographies

Dr. Doug S. Cairns is currently a Research Associate and Manager of the Advanced Composites Technology Department at Hercules Advanced Materials and Systems Company (HAMSCO). His duties include developing a basic understanding of the performance of advanced composites for primary structural applications including fracture, fatigue, and longevity. Dr. Cairns received a Doctor of Philosophy in Aeronautics and Astronautics from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in 1987 where he did research on the damage resistance and damage tolerance of composites under impact loading in the Technology Laboratory for Advanced Composites (TELAC). Previously, he was a Senior Design Engineer at Hercules Aerospace Company, developing analyses and damage tolerance criteria for large filament wound solid rocket boosters. He worked as a Staff Engineer in the Composites Materials Research Group (CMRG) at the University of Wyoming where he received a Master's Degree in 1981 and a Bachelor's Degree in 1978 in Mechanical Engineering. He is a member of SAMPE, AIAA, ASME and the honorary societies of Sigma XI and Sigma Gamma Tau.

Joel F. Campbell is currently a Senior Physicist in the Physics Group of Hercules Aerospace Company. He is responsible for new sensor development for composite materials. Previously, he was a Research Scientist at China Lake Naval Weapons Center where his responsibilities included developing analytical and numerical modeling of nonlinear optics and microwave communication. Mr. Campbell is a Doctor of Philosophy candidate in Solid State Physics at the University of Utah where he received Master of Science degree in 1985 and a Bachelor of Science degree in 1982 (Cum Laude).

Dr. Bert J. Vanderheiden is currently a Senior Research Scientist and Supervisor in the Physics Group of Hercules Aerospace Company. He is the Principal Investigator of Non-Destructive Inspection projects. His professional interests include ultrasonic C-Scan, NMR and opto-acoustic waveguides. Dr. Vanderheiden received a Ph.D. in Solid State Physics from the University of Utah in 1988 where he conducted research on NMR inspection of thin-film semi-conductors. He received a Bachelor of Science in Physics (Cum Laude) from the University of Utah in 1982. He is a member of the American Society of Physics and the Society of Quantitative Non-Destructive Evaluation (QNDE).

Dr. Mohamed G. Abdallah is a Senior Research Scientist in the Advanced Composites Technology Department at Hercules Advanced Materials and Systems Company (HAMSCO) where he has worked since 1982. He received a Ph.D. in Applied Mechanics from the University of Houston in 1982, a Master of Science in Mechanical Engineering from the Louisiana State University in 1973 and a Bachelor of Science in Mechanical Engineering from the Assiut University in Egypt in 1965. His professional interests include experimental mechanics of advanced composite materials, high resolution moire interferometry and Non-Destructive Evaluation of composite materials. Previously, he worked for Exxon Production Research Co., Brow and Root and C.R. Bean. Dr. Abdallah is a registered Professional Engineer in Utah, Texas and Louisiana. He is a member of ASME, SEM and the honorary society of Tau Beta Pi.

Larry J. Martinez is currently a Senior Technical Specialist in the Physics Group of Hercules Aerospace Company where he has worked since 1977. His professional interests include ultrasonic C-Scan inspection, computed tomography, thermography, opto-acoustic waveguides and acoustic emission in advanced composites. Mr. Martinez is an ASNT-certified ultrasonic inspection specialist where his expertise includes inspection of large composite structures.

Figure 1. Backbone structure of polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF).

Figure 2. Poled PVDF.

Figure 3. Charge Amplifier Setup

Figure 4. Test Coupon Configuration

Figure 5. Stress-Strain relationship for 90 degree AS4/3501-6 laminate.

Figure 6. Piezo film response for 90 degree AS4/3501-6 laminate

Figure 7. Predicted versus measured piezo film response on aluminum sample.

Figure 8. Predicted versus measured piezo film response for [+45]₄₄ AS/3501-6

Figure 9. Voltage Output as a Function of Temperature From Piezo Sensor (mounted on AS4/3401-6 [+45/0/-45/90]₂ quasi-isotropic laminate)

Figure 10. Response of piezo film to cyclic loading (>1 Hz).

Figure 11. Transient response of piezo film during low velocity impact.

Through Transmission Mode

Figure 12. Through Transmission Non-Destructive Evaluation (NDE) setup of piezo films

Figure 13. Through-transmission NDE response of piezo film Figure 14. Pulse-echo (NDE) response using piezo films

Figure 15. Pulse-Echo imaging using piezo films

Figure 16. Specimen configuration for Acoustic Emission (AE) monitoring

Figure 17. Cumulative AE events - piezo crystal versus piezo film.

Figure 18. Fracture location identification using piezo films as AE monitors.

